

Edge Antimagic Total Labeling of Graphs

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Abstract: The definition of (a, d) -edge-antimagic total labeling was introduced by Simanjuntak, Bertault and Miller as a natural extension of edge-magic labeling defined by Kotzig and Rosa. The present paper deals with a class of subdivided star for all possible values of the parameter $d \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

Key Words: Smarandachely super (a, d) -edge-antimagic total labeling, super (a, d) -EAT labeling, subdivision of stars.

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§1. Introduction

All graphs in this paper are finite, undirected and simple. For a graph G we denote the vertex-set and edge-set by $V(G)$ and $E(G)$, respectively. A (v, e) -graph G is a graph such that $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$. A general reference for graph-theoretic ideas can be seen [21]. There are many types of labeling, for example magic, antimagic, gracegraceful, odd gracefu, cordial, radio, sum and mean labeling. This paper deals with different results on super (a, d) -edge-antimagic total $((a, d) - EAT)$ labelings for a subclass of a subdivided star trees. The more details on antimagic total labeling can be seen in [5,9]. The subject of edge-magic total labeling of graphs has its origin in the works of Kotzig and Rosa [12, 13] on what they called magic valuations of graphs. The definition of (a, d) -edge-antimagic total labeling was introduced by Simanjuntak, Bertault and Miller in [18] as a natural extension of edge-magic labeling defined by Kotzig and Rosa.

Conjecture 1.1([6]) *Every tree admits a super edge-magic total labeling.*

For supporting this conjecture, many authors have considered super edge-magic total labeling for many particular classes of trees for example [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 16, 17, 18, 19]. Lee and Shah [14] verified this conjecture by a computer search for trees with at most 17 vertices. However, this conjecture is still as an open problem.

A star is a particular type of tree graph and many authors have proved the magicness for subdivided stars. Ngurah et. al. [15] proved that $T(m, n, k)$ is also super edge-magic if $k = n + 3$ or $n + 4$. In [20], Salman et. al. found the super edge-magic total labeling of a

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subdivision of a star S_n^m for $m = 1, 2$. Javaid et. al. [11] proved super edge-magic total labeling on subdivided star $K_{1,4}$ and w-trees.

However, super (a, d) -edge-antimagic total labeling of $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_r)$ for different $\{n_i : 1 \leq i \leq r\}$ is still open.

Definition 1.1 A graph G is called (a, d) -edge-antimagic total $((a, d) - EAT)$ if there exist integers $a > 0$, $d \geq 0$ and a bijection

$$\lambda : V(G) \cup E(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, v + e\}$$

such that $W = \{w(xy) : xy \in E(G)\}$ forms an arithmetic sequence starting from a with the common difference d , where $w(xy) = \lambda(x) + \lambda(y) + \lambda(xy)$ for every $xy \in E(G)$. W is called the set of edge-weights of the graph G .

Furthermore, let $H \leq G$. If there is a bijective function $\lambda : V(H) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |H|\}$ such that the set of edge-sums of all edges in H forms an arithmetic progression $\{a, a + d, a + 2d, \dots, a + (|E(H)| - 1)d\}$ but for all edges not in H is a constant, such a labeling is called a Smarandachely (a, d) -edge-antimagic labeling of G respect to H . Clearly, an (a, d) -EAV labeling of G is a Smarandachely (s, d) -EAV labeling of G respect to G itself.

Definition 1.2 A (a, d) -edge-antimagic total labeling λ is called super (a, d) -edge-antimagic total labeling if $\lambda(V(G)) = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, v\}$.

Lemma 1.1([3]) If f is a super edge-magic total labeling of G with the magic constant c , then the function $f_1 : V(G) \cup E(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, v + e\}$ defined by

$$f_1(x) = \begin{cases} v + 1 - f(x), & \text{for } x \in V(G), \\ 2v + e + 1 - f(x), & \text{for } x \in E(G). \end{cases}$$

is also a super edge-magic total labeling of G with the magic constant $c_1 = 4v + e + 3 - c$.

Definition 1.3 For $n_i \geq 1$ and $r \geq 3$, let $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_p)$ be a graph obtained by inserting $n_i - 1$ vertices to each of the i -th edge of the star $K_{1,p}$, where $1 \leq i \leq p$.

§2. Main Results

We consider the following proposition which we will use frequently in the main results.

Proposition 2.1([4]) If a (v, e) -graph G has a (s, d) -EAV labeling then

- (1) G has a super $(s + v + 1, d + 1)$ -EAT labeling;
- (2) G has a super $(s + v + e, d - 1)$ -EAT labeling.

Theorem 2.1 For all positive integers n , $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4)$ admits super $(a, 0)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + e + s$ and admits super $(a, 2)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + s + 1$, where $n_1 = n, n_2 = n + 1, n_3 = 2n + 1, n_4 = 4n + 2, s = 4n + 5$.

Proof Suppose that the vertex-set and edge-set of G are as follows:

$$V(G) = \{c\} \cup \{x_i^{l_i} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 4; 1 \leq l_i \leq n_i\},$$

$$E(G) = \{c x_i^{l_i} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 4\} \cup \{x_i^{l_i} x_i^{l_i+1} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 4; 1 \leq l_i \leq n_i - 1\}.$$

If $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$ then $v = 8n + 5$ and $e = v - 1$.

We define the labeling $\eta : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |V(G)|\}$ as follows:

$\eta(c) = 4(n + 1)$. For l_i odd $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{l_1+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1}, \\ (n+2) - \frac{l_2+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2}, \\ (2n+3) - \frac{l_3+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ 4(n+1) - \frac{l_4+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}. \end{cases}$$

For l_i even $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} 4(n+1) + \frac{l_1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1}, \\ 5(n+1) - \frac{l_2}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2}, \\ (6n+5) - \frac{l_3}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ (8n+6) - \frac{l_4}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}. \end{cases}$$

The set of all edge-sums $\{\eta(x) + \eta(y) : xy \in E(G)\} = \{4n + 4 + j : 1 \leq j \leq e\}$ form an arithmetic sequence starting with minimum edge-sum $4(n + 1)$. Therefore, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 0)$ -EAT labeling and we obtain the magic constant $a = v + e + s = 20n + 14$. Similarly, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 2)$ -EAT labeling and we obtain the minimum edge weight is $a = v + 1 + s = 12n + 11$. \square

Theorem 2.2 *For all positive integers n , $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4)$ admits super $(a, 1)$ -EAT labeling with $a = 2v + s - 1$ and admits super $(a, 3)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + s + 1$, where $v = |V(G)|$, $s = 3$, $n_1 = n$, $n_2 = n + 1$, $n_3 = 2n + 1$, $n_4 = 4n + 2$.*

Proof Suppose that the $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ are defined as in the proof of the Theorem 2.1. Let us consider $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$ then $v = (8n + 5)$ and $e = 4(2n + 1)$. We define the vertex labeling $\eta : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |V(G)|\}$ as follows:

$\eta(c) = 2$. For $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$ with $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} l_1, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1} \text{ and } l_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ 2 + l_1, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1} \text{ and } l_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ (2n+1) - (l_2 - 1), & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2} \text{ and } l_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ (2n+2) - (l_2 - 2), & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2} \text{ and } l_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 4(n+1) - l_3, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ (8n+6) - l_4, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \end{cases}$$

The set of edge-sums $\{\eta(x) + \eta(y) : xy \in E(G)\}$ generated by the above scheme forms a integer sequence $3, 3+2, \dots, 3+2(e-1)$ with difference difference 2. Therefore, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a,1)$ -EAT labeling and the minimum edge weight is $a = v + e + s = 2(v + 1)$ Similarly, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a,3)$ -EAT labeling and the minimum edge weight is $a = v + 1 + s = v + 4$. \square

Theorem 2.3 *For all positive integers n , $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5)$ admits super $(a,0)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + e + s$ and admits super $(a,2)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + s + 1$, where $n_1 = n$, $n_2 = n + 1$, $n_3 = 2n + 1$, $n_4 = 4n + 2$, $n_5 = 8n + 4$ and $s = 8(n + 1)$.*

Proof Suppose that the vertex-set and edge-set of the graph G are as follows:

$$V(G) = \{c\} \cup \{x_i^{l_i} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 5; 1 \leq l_i \leq n_i\},$$

$$E(G) = \{c x_i^1 \mid 1 \leq i \leq 5\} \cup \{x_i^{l_i} x_i^{l_i+1} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 5; 1 \leq l_i \leq n_i - 1\}.$$

If $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$ then $v = 16n + 9$ and $e = 8(2n + 1)$. We define the labeling $\eta : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |V(G)|\}$ as follows:

$\eta(c) = 8n + 6$. For l_i odd $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{l_1+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1}, \\ (n+2) - \frac{l_2+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2}, \\ (2n+3) - \frac{l_3+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ 4(n+1) - \frac{l_4+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \\ (8n+6) - \frac{l_5+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_5^{l_5}. \end{cases}$$

For l_i even $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} (8n+6) + \frac{l_1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1}, \\ (9n+7) - \frac{l_2}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2}, \\ (10n+6) - \frac{l_3}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ (12n+8) - \frac{l_4}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \\ (16n+9) - \frac{l_5}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_5^{l_5}. \end{cases}$$

The set of all edge-sums $\{\eta(x) + \eta(y) : xy \in E(G)\} = \{8n + 6 + j : 1 \leq j \leq e\}$ form an arithmetic sequence starting with minimum edge-sum $(8n + 7)$. Therefore, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a,0)$ -EAT labeling and we obtain the magic constant $a = v + e + s = 40n + 25$. Similarly, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a,2)$ -EAT labeling and the minimum edge weight is $a = v + 1 + s = 24n + 18$. \square

Theorem 2.4 *For all positive integers n , $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5)$ admits super $(a,1)$ -EAT labeling with $a = 2v + s - 1$ and admits super $(a,3)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + s + 1$, where $v = |V(G)|$, $s = 3$, $n_1 = n$, $n_2 = n + 1$, $n_3 = 2n + 1$, $n_4 = 4n + 2$.*

Proof Suppose that the $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ are defined as in the proof of the Theorem 2.3.

Let us consider $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$ then $v = 16n + 9$ and $e = 8(2n + 1)$. We define the vertex labeling $\eta : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |V(G)|\}$ as follows:

$\eta(c) = 2$. For $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} l_1, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1} \text{ and } l_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ 2 + l_1, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1} \text{ and } l_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ (2n + 1) - (l_2 - 1), & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2} \text{ and } l_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ 2(n + 1) - (l_2 - 2), & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2} \text{ and } l_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 4(n + 1) - l_3, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ 2(4n + 3) - l_4, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \\ 2(8n + 5) - l_5, & \text{for } u = x_5^{l_5}. \end{cases}$$

The set of edge-sums $\{\eta(x) + \eta(y) : xy \in E(G)\}$ generated by the above scheme forms a integer sequence $3, 3+2, \dots, 3+2(e-1)$ with difference difference 2. Therefore, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 1)$ -EAT labeling and the minimum edge weight is $a = v + e + s = 2(v + 1)$. Similarly, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 3)$ -EAT labeling and the minimum edge weight is $a = v + 1 + s = v + 4$.

Theorem 2.5 *For all positive integers n , $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5, n_6, \dots, n_p)$ admits super $(a, 0)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + e + s$ and admits super $(a, 2)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + s + 1$, where $n_1 = n, n_2 = n + 1, n_3 = 2n + 1, n_4 = 4n + 2, n_5 = 8n + 4$,*

$$s = 8(n + 1) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-3}(2n + 1)] \quad \text{and } n_m = 2^{m-3}(2n + 1)$$

for $6 \leq m \leq p$.

Proof Suppose that the vertex-set and edge-set of G are as follows:

$$V(G) = \{c\} \cup \{x_i^{l_i} \mid 1 \leq i \leq p; 1 \leq l_i \leq n_i\},$$

$$E(G) = \{c x_i^1 \mid 1 \leq i \leq p\} \cup \{x_i^{l_i} x_i^{l_i+1} \mid 1 \leq i \leq p; 1 \leq l_i \leq n_i - 1\}.$$

If $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$ then

$$v = (16n + 9) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-2}(2n + 1)] \quad \text{and} \quad e = (16n + 8) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-2}(2n + 1)].$$

We define the labeling $\eta : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |V(G)|\}$ as follows:

$$\eta(c) = (8n + 6) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-3}(2n + 1)].$$

For l_i odd $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $6 \leq m \leq p$ we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{l_1+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1}, \\ (n+2) - \frac{l_2+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2}, \\ (2n+3) - \frac{l_3+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ 4(n+1) - \frac{l_4+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \\ (8n+6) - \frac{l_5+1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_5^{l_5}. \end{cases}$$

and

$$\eta(x_i^{l_i}) = (8n+6) + \sum_{m=6}^i [2^{m-3}(2n+1)] - \frac{l_i+1}{2}$$

respectively. For l_i even $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $\eta(c) = \beta$ we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} \beta + \frac{l_1}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1}, \\ (\beta+n) - \frac{l_2}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2}, \\ (\beta+2n-1) - \frac{l_3}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ (\beta+4n+1) - \frac{l_4}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \\ (\beta+8n+3) - \frac{l_5}{2}, & \text{for } u = x_5^{l_5}. \end{cases}$$

and

$$\eta(x_i^{l_i}) = (\beta+8n+3) + \sum_{m=6}^i [2^{m-3}(2n+1)] - \frac{l_i}{2}$$

respectively. The set of all edge-sums $\{\eta(x) + \eta(y) : xy \in E(G)\} = \{\beta + j : 1 \leq j \leq e\}$ form an arithmetic sequence starting with minimum edge-sum β . Therefore, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 0)$ -EAT labeling and we obtain the magic constant

$$a = v + e + s = (2v + 8n + 7) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-3}(2n+1)]$$

Similarly, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 2)$ -EAT labeling and obtain the minimum edge weight is

$$a = v + 1 + s = (v + 8n + 9) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-3}(2n+1)]. \quad \square$$

Theorem 2.6 For all positive integers n , $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5, n_6, \dots, n_p)$ admits super $(a, 1)$ -EAT labeling with $a = 2v + s - 1$ and admits super $(a, 3)$ -EAT labeling with $a = v + s + 1$, where $v = |V(G)|$, $s = 3$, $n_1 = n$, $n_2 = n + 1$, $n_3 = 2n + 1$, $n_4 = 4n + 2$, $n_5 = 8n + 4$,

$$s = 8(n+1) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-3}(2n+1)] \quad \text{and} \quad n_m = 2^{m-3}(2n+1)$$

for $6 \leq m \leq p$.

Proof Suppose that the $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ are defined as in the proof of the Theorem 2.5. Let us consider $v = |V(G)|$ and $e = |E(G)|$ then

$$v = (16n + 9) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-2}(2n + 1)] \quad \text{and} \quad e = 8(2n + 1) + \sum_{m=6}^p [2^{m-2}(2n + 1)].$$

We define the vertex labeling $\eta : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, V(G)\}$ as follows:

$\eta(c) = 2$. For $1 \leq l_i \leq n_i$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $6 \leq m \leq p$, we define

$$\eta(u) = \begin{cases} l_1, & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1} \text{ and } l_1 \equiv 1(\text{mod}2), \\ (2 + l_1), & \text{for } u = x_1^{l_1} \text{ and } l_1 \equiv 0(\text{mod}2), \\ (2n + 1) - (l_2 - 1), & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2} \text{ and } l_2 \equiv 1(\text{mod}2), \\ 2(n + 1) - (l_2 - 2), & \text{for } u = x_2^{l_2} \text{ and } l_2 \equiv 0(\text{mod}2), \\ 4(n + 1) - l_3, & \text{for } u = x_3^{l_3}, \\ (8n + 6) - l_4, & \text{for } u = x_4^{l_4}, \\ (16n + 10) - l_5, & \text{for } u = x_5^{l_5}. \end{cases}$$

and

$$\eta(x_i^{l_i}) = (16n + 10) + \sum_{m=6}^i [2^{m-3}(2n + 1)] - l_i$$

respectively. The set of edge-sums $\{\eta(x) + \eta(y) : xy \in E(G)\}$ generated by the above scheme forms a integer sequence $3, 3 + 2, \dots, 3 + 2(e - 1)$ with difference difference 2. Therefore, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 1)$ -EAT labeling and obtain the minimum edge weight is $a = v + e + s = 2(v + 1)$ Similarly, by Proposition 2.1, η can be extended to a super $(a, 3)$ -EAT labeling and obtain the minimum edge weight is $a = v + 1 + s = v + 4$. \square

§3. Conclusion

In this paper, we show that a subclass of a tree, namely a subdivision of a star tree denoted by $G \cong T(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_p)$ admits super (a, d) -EAT labeling for all positive integers n and all possible values of the parameter d . However, for different values of the minimum edge-weight a and n_i , problem is still open.

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